

Original Research Article

Gender Effect On Olfactory Perception In Young Adults Aged 17-18 Years Measured By Free-Identification Method

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1. Introduction

1.1. Olfactory Epithelium

The initial steps of olfactory perception happen in the olfactory epithelium, located in the nasal cavity (figure 1) (Manzini, Frasnelli, & Croy, 2014). The epithelium is a type of body tissue lining internal and external surfaces of the body such as organs and glands. This is made up of basal cells, supporting cells and olfactory receptor neurons. Basal cells are a type of neural progenitor cells, meaning that they can specialise into a few specific cells. Their job is to regenerate the supporting cells and olfactory receptor neurons. Supporting cells produce mucus along with the Bowman's glands, maintain ionic balance and synthesise neuromodulators. Mucus is required to trap and neutralise harmful substances. The ionic concentration in the mucus needs to be stable as changes will affect the olfactory transduction process (Bryche, Baly, & Meunier, 2021), i.e. the binding of odour molecules to the receptor cells and the subsequent signal sent to the brain (NCI, 2022). Neuromodulators are substances that do not directly activate ion-channel receptors, but act with neurotransmitters to do so (Brittanica, 2022). The olfactory receptor neurons are bipolar, meaning they have two projections from their cell body. They have a dendrite which extends into the epithelial surface. On the surface of the dendrite are many non-motile (non-moving) cilia in the mucus with access to the odour molecules (Purves, Augustine, & Fitzpatrick, 2001). Olfactory receptor neurons also have a projection into an unmyelinated axon. Olfactory receptor neurons need to be regenerated by basal cells to resolve the issue of their inevitable damage by harmful antigens and particles like pollutants in the atmosphere.

1.2. Measuring Olfactory Perception

The most common method of measuring olfactory perception is through odour identification (Sorokowski, et al., 2019). This can be done by 'free-identification' where no support is given, or by 'cued-identification' where a number of options are provided, and the participant has to choose.

1.3. Olfactory Transduction

Olfactory transduction begins when odour molecules bind to specific receptors on the external surface of the cilia (Purves, Augustine, & Fitzpatrick, 2001). This can happen directly or through proteins in the mucus called odourant binding proteins, which isolate the odour and send it to the receptor. Olfactory receptor neurons have specific G-proteins which are activated when odourants bind to the receptor protein on the cell membrane of the olfactory

receptor neuron. The G-protein in turn, activates an adenylate cyclase (an enzyme), which converts ATP into cAMP by removing two phosphates. The cAMP in turn activates a cation-selective channel, permitting the influx of Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions into the cilia, resulting in depolarisation. The influx of Ca²⁺ ions opens another gated channel, which releases Cl⁻ ions, further depolarising the membrane potential. When the depolarisation reaches

a threshold of -55mV , the cell fires an action potential that travels along the rest of the neuron in one direction (Mackenna & Callander, 1990). To stop the depolarisation from repeating and reaching a high magnitude, the Ca^{2+} ions then bind to calmodulin proteins which reduce the amount of cAMP in the membrane. Finally, Ca^{2+} ions leave through the $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Na}^{+}$ exchange pathway, restoring the ionic balance after the action potential has left the cell.

Olfactory Pathway to Brain

The axons projected from the olfactory receptor neurons combine with other receptor cell axons, making up bundles of nerve fibres just below the cribriform plate, a portion of the ethmoid bone which is on the roof of the nose (Perry, 2022). These axonal bundles are known as the olfactory nerve (CNI, meaning the first cranial nerve). The CNI terminates at the olfactory bulb, known as a relay station within the pathway. Within the olfactory bulb are bundles of nerve fibres, glomeruli, where the axons make connections to the dendrites of mitral relay neurons. The olfactory cortex is a combination of areas in the brain which receive the impulse from the olfactory bulb, and the odour information is then processed and registered by the human.

1.4. Effect of Gender on Olfactory Perception

1.4.1. Hormonal effect

Published investigations on sex differences in olfactory perception typically yield results showing that females are more sensitive, or that there is no difference between either sex (Doty & E Leslie, 2009). Most studies look at whether the female hormones oestrogen, progesterone, Follicle-stimulating Hormone (FSH) and Luteinising Hormone (LH) have an effect on olfactory sensitivity. One experiment was conducted on rodents, which suggested that oestrogen may serve a role in affecting the hypothalamus, which controls the body's circadian rhythm (Bourne & Zukerman, 1940). The circadian rhythm can be described as the body's internal clock, which has been suggested to have a role in olfactory sensitivity due to evolution. After meals, wild animals could have been more drawn to human groups, resulting in humans being more sensitive to smells depending on what the biological clock's time is for eating (Herz, 2017). If these humans were to have heightened olfactory sensitivity, it would allow them to better detect their predators. Natural selection could have caused this trait to become present in humans. In natural selection, the organisms with the most well adapted traits (in this case heightened olfactory sensitivity after eating) will survive and reproduce, passing on the alleles to the next generation. If oestrogen has an effect on the natural circadian rhythm, this could result in heightened olfactory sensitivity.

2. Aim of the study

To verify the influence of gender in young adults on the olfactory perception of 5 odours: rose water, caramel, lemon mint, peppermint, vanilla.

3. Objectives

3.1. Primary objective

To evaluate the effect of gender in young adults (17-18 years) males and females in their ability to identify odours of rose, caramel, lemon mint, peppermint and vanilla when presented separately as a drop on filter paper.

3.2. Secondary objectives

- To compare the average time for recognition of odours by young adult males and females
- To compare the average retention time of different odours in young adult males and females
- To compare liked and disliked odours between young adult males and females

4. Materials and method

4.1. Variables

- Dependent: Odour (categorical data), time to perceive (numerical data), odour retention time (numerical data), liked/disliked odours (categorical data)

- Independent: Gender (categorical data, male and female), Scents (categorical data, rose water, caramel, lemon mint, peppermint, vanilla)

Table 1 Control Variables

Control Variable	How it can affect the data	Management
Volume/Concentration of scents	A higher volume/concentration of essence used will make certain scents stronger, so they will be perceived for longer as compared to other scents	The same volume of water (99 cm ³) will be used with the same volume/concentration of essence (1ml; 2% solution), so all scents are the same volume/concentration of 100ml; 0.02%
Volume of scent dropped on filter paper	A higher volume of scent used with filter paper will make it last longer as compared to other scents	One drop of the scent will be placed on the filter paper
Distance of filter paper from nose	A higher distance from the paper will make it harder to recognise the scent, so it will not last as long	All participants will be asked to keep the paper 1cm away from nostrils, this will be judged by eye
Environment of room	If conducted in a laboratory/dining area, there could be scents of chemicals/food which reduces the strength of the scents in the experiment	Use a room without any scents present (not conducted in kitchen, laboratory), and where perfume/scented candles/freshener was not used
Colour of bottles containing scents	If the colour of the solutions are seen by the participant, it could influence what they guess the scent to be	Opaque bottles were used which were further wrapped with tape so the colour of the solution could not be seen

4.2. Study population

4.2.1 Ethics statement: The study was started after obtaining permission from the school and after obtaining written, informed consent from participants. All the data was deidentified and kept anonymous.

4.2.2 Exclusion criteria for experiment

1. History of allergy or intolerance to any of the previously mentioned odours
2. History of upper respiratory tract infection in the past 14 days
3. History of allergic rhinitis, nasal polyps
4. Current usage of medications such as nasal sprays that can interfere with odour perception

4.3. Materials and method

The free-identification method was chosen, a common method for measuring odour perception (Sorokowski, et al., 2019).

4.3.1. Preparation

- This was done in the BISAD school laboratory
- Water was measured (99cm³) using a measuring cylinder of $\pm 0.5\text{cm}^3$ and poured into a 100cm³ opaque plastic bottle
- Rose essence was added (1cm³ of 2% solution), measured using a pipette of $\pm 0.05\text{cm}^3$ to form 0.02% rose essence. The same was done for the other 4 essences.

- Using a measuring cylinder, 100cm³ water was poured in a bottle (for the control)
- All the bottles were covered in opaque tape. They were then labelled with numbers and names of the scent were recorded according to their number
- The 5 coffee filter papers were folded 4 times and cut up, making several of small strips of paper to be used with the essence

4.3.2. Experiment

- Students aged 17-18 years studying at BISAD, UAE who were willing to participate in this study were screened for eligibility criteria. Students were divided in to 2 groups of 10 males and 10 females each
- The experiment was performed in an empty room inside the school without any previous scents present, far away from the laboratories and cafeteria
- The procedure was explained to the volunteers. The volunteer was asked to raise hands at the onset of olfactory perception and announce when at the end of perception. They would then be asked to identify the scent. To prevent the carry-on effect of one odour, the individuals were exposed to the odour of coffee initially and after every test substance
- One drop of rose essence was poured onto coffee filter-paper strip. The procedure above was carried out. Response, time, and the name of the scent were recorded in the data record form. The used filter paper was disposed. The same was done for the other 4 essences, and for water
- The participants were repeatedly exposed to the scents 3 times in total which were spread out so the same scent was never used twice in a row. The average time was then calculated for recognition and scent wear off
- The most preferred and disliked odour was also recorded at the end

4.4. Statistical Tests

- Chi-square test will be used to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between males and females in odour identification and liked/disliked odours, as it is a measurement of categorical data (dealing with proportions)
- Mean time to perceive each odour, will be compared between the 2 genders using the independent t-test, as this compares the mean of two groups
- The calculated P value will be used to determine if there is significant difference between males and females liked/disliked odours, time taken to recognise scent and time taken for loss of scent. A P value less than 0.05 will be considered significant
- The chi squared test and independent t-test was performed using IBM SPSS software, and the P value was calculated using the same software (IBM, 2022)

Chi square test was used to calculate the P value for liked/disliked odours between males and females. The expected value for each odour was 5 correct out of 10 participants.

Independent t-test was used to calculate the P value for time of odour perception/identification between males and females.

5. Results

The raw data can be seen in the appendix. It is different from the processed data in that it shows the mean time for each participant in odour recognition and retention, not overall for both genders.

5.1. Uncertainty Calculations

The uncertainty for using the stopwatch is ± 0.2 seconds due to human error (KeyStageWiki, 2023).

The absolute uncertainty of the total volume of scent solutions formed can be calculated. To do this, the absolute uncertainties of the individual measurements should be added as both units are th

5.2. Qualitative Data

Most of the female students could name an odour quickly (within 30 seconds of initial recognition) but the male students had difficulty in remembering the exact names of the odours that aligned with what they smelled, most of them taking 2 minutes or longer after initial recognition.

All students realised within 10 seconds that the paper with water did not have any scent and they identified that it was water, however, some of them knew that it would be used as a control due to their knowledge of lab experiments.

5.3. Processed Data

To process the data, the identification column was changed to show whether the student guessed correctly, instead of the scent they guessed. Furthermore, gender was put as a number instead of a letter, and the liked/disliked odours were placed in a new table with frequency and percentages according to the 5 scents. The mean times were also calculated for both genders by summing the mean times for all participants in each gender and dividing it by the number of male/female students.

For identification, 1=correct and 2=incorrect.

Table 2 Identification, time for recognition, time for loss of scent for both genders

Gender	Mean Age	Rose Water			Caramel			Lemon Mint			Peppermint			Vanilla		
		Percentage Correct in Identifying (%)	Mean Time to Recognise (s)	Mean time for Loss (s)	Percentage Correct in Identifying (%)	Mean Time to Recognise (s)	Mean time for Loss (s)	Percentage Correct in Identifying (%)	Mean Time to Recognise (s)	Mean time for Loss (s)	Percentage Correct in Identifying (%)	Mean Time to Recognise (s)	Mean time for Loss (s)	Percentage Correct in Identifying (%)	Mean Time to Recognise (s)	Mean time for Loss (s)
Female	17.50	70	1.06	208.95	90	1.08	290.89	90	1.03	205.28	80	1.05	218.69	80	1.04	288.04
Male	17.40	40	1.14	116.67	50	1.06	183.25	70	1.07	159.03	80	1.05	198.42	50	1.04	192.81

From Table 2, overall, it is noticeable that female students identified the odours better across all five scents, with 70% or more of the female students having guessed correctly, meanwhile 40% or more of the male students had guessed correctly. Furthermore, they retained the scent for the odours for longer periods of time than males e.g. 205.98s for females compared to 159.03s for males for the peppermint scent. However, there doesn't seem to be any major difference in the time to register each scent.

Figure 1 Pie chart of percentage of liked odours for females

Figure 2 Pie chart of percentage of liked odours for males

From the pie charts above (figures 1 and 2), vanilla was the favourite scent for females, and rose water for males. Lemon Mint was liked by 2 students for both genders, and the rest of the scents (caramel, peppermint) had 0-10% of students liking them for both genders.

Table 3 Disliked odour percentages for males and females

Disliked Odour	Females (%)	Males (%)
Rose	20	10
Caramel	50	20
Lemon mint	0	30
Peppermint	20	30
Vanilla	10	10

From the table, it can be seen that caramel was the most disliked odour for females, on the other hand, it was lemon mint and peppermint for males. Also, none of the females disliked lemon mint.

5.4. Statistical Analysis

All statistical tests were performed using SPSS version 22

The statistical analysis by chi-square testing shows that there was no significant difference in which odours were liked/disliked for both genders as the P values were larger than 0.05.

Table 4 Statistical analysis of frequency of odours guessed correctly for both genders

Odours	Percentage of Females Correct in Odour Identification (%)	Percentage of Males Correct in Odour Identification (%)	P value
Rose	70	40	0.370
Caramel	90	50	0.410
Lemon mint	90	70	0.580
Pepper mint	80	80	1.000

Statistical analysis in Table 4 above by chi-square testing shows that there was no significant difference in the number of males and females who guessed each odour correctly, as all P values are larger than 0.05.

Table 5 Statistical analysis of retention of odour perception for both genders, significant values are highlighted

Odours	Female Mean Duration of Odour Retention (s)	Male Mean Duration of Odour Retention (s)	P value
Rose	207.90	115.00	<0.001
Caramel	289.80	182.18	0.002
Lemon mint	204.20	157.90	0.016
Peppermint	217.60	197.00	0.416
Vanilla	287.00	191.70	0.003

Statistical analysis in Table 5 by independent t-testing shows that there was a significant difference in the duration of odour perception between males and females for all highlighted scents where $P < 0.05$. However, there wasn't a significant difference for the peppermint scent.

Table 6 Statistical analysis of time for recognition of scents

Odours	Mean Female Time until Odour Recognition (s)	Mean Male Time until Odour Recognition (s)	P value
Rose	1.00	1.13	0.230
Caramel	1.07	1.06	0.670
Lemon mint	1.03	1.07	0.160
Pepper mint	1.05	1.04	0.940
Vanilla	1.03	1.03	0.880

Statistical analysis in table 6 by independent t-testing shows that there was no significant difference in the time taken to register scents for male and female students, as the P values are greater than 0.05.

6. Conclusion and Future directions

The independent t-tests reveal that gender does not have any significant impact on odour identification, time for odour recognition and liked/disliked odours for all 5 odours used in this experiment: rose water, caramel, lemon mint, peppermint, and vanilla. On the other hand, it revealed that there is a significant difference in the duration of odour perception in four of the scents: rose water, caramel, lemon mint and vanilla, with female students having longer odour perception. The null hypothesis can be accepted as the statistical test showed gender doesn't have a significant impact on odour identification. However, the secondary objective of olfactory sensitivity revealed a significant difference by the independent t-test performed. This showed that young adult females perceive odours for much longer times than male students e.g. 207.9s compared to 115s for rose water.

The greater amount of the oestrogen hormone in females may affect the hypothalamus region of the brain thus influencing the biological clock to interpret the time as post-mealtime (G Bourne, 1940). Due to natural selection, humans have evolved to have heightened olfactory sensitivity after meals to be aware of predators. However, this is not a confirmed scientific explanation, and it was verified if students had eaten before the investigation, so another hormone (progesterone, FSH, LH) or metabolic pathway may influence olfactory sensitivity.

Since most of the investigations on sex differences in olfactory perception try to explain varying sensitivity by female hormones, an investigation can be done on post-menopausal women when hormone levels are low, and this can be compared to pre-menopausal women to see if there is a significant difference in olfactory perception (Cleveland Clinic, 2021).

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